

Production of solar hydrogen through photocatalysis by CdS and CdS/ZnS modified by Pt, Ag₂S and Si[†]

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Abstract : Photocatalytic production of solar hydrogen using CdS suspensions in aqueous solution containing Na₂S-Na₂SO₃ has been studied. CdS prepared from different sources show different photocatalytic activity towards generation of hydrogen. CdS alone as well as modified by doping materials such as Pt, Ag₂S and Si and mixing with ZnS has been investigated. When unmodified CdS is mixed with ZnS, the photocatalytic efficiency of CdS is enhanced and becomes maximum at a particular composition. When CdS is doped, the efficiency increases and in each case the best result is obtained at different particular composition.

Keywords : Photocatalysis, solar energy, hydrogen, CdS.

Introduction

The increasing demand for energy has greatly stimulated research into new sources of energy during the last few decades. Solar energy is of great interest because it is inexhaustible. Nature makes extensive use of this energy source in photosynthesis, a process in which solar energy is converted into chemical energy. Because of high cost and low efficiency for the conversion of solar energy into electrical energy, there has been an increasing interest in photoelectrochemical devices for conversion of solar energy into chemical energy. These devices consist mainly of semiconductor/electrolyte junctions which can easily be made. Attention has been focused on the production of hydrogen from natural sources, like water, by irradiating single semiconductors¹⁻¹³ as well as mixed semiconductor suspensions^{5,14-17}. The development of photocatalytic systems capable of using the visible region of the solar spectrum by semiconductor suspensions has been done in the following ways : (a) large band gap semiconductors aided by photosensitizers, (b) small band gap semiconductors and (c) mixture of large and small band gap semiconductors. Kraeutler and Bard¹⁸ and others¹⁹⁻²⁴ have

shown that a large band gap semiconductor TiO₂, surface modified by deposition of platinum, can act as an excellent photocatalyst. However, semiconductors having band gap less than that of TiO₂ is preferable for solar energy conversion as TiO₂ absorbs only UV light, a very small fraction of solar radiation reaching the earth. CdS is a small band gap semiconductor and has been used as a photocatalyst for evolution of hydrogen by sunlight because of its sufficiently negative flat band potential and good absorption properties in the visible region of the solar spectrum. On irradiation, these semiconductors undergo anodic decomposition. It is, therefore, necessary to prevent photocorrosion by using sacrificial substrates, especially agents like sulphide and/or sulphite²⁵⁻³². In aqueous medium at high pH (say pH 13), with CdS particles, we have

[†]Dedicated to Professor Suresh C. Ameta on his 60th birthday.

If we have S^{2-} and SO_3^{2-} in solution,

The reaction of h^+ (hole) with S^{2-} is kinetically favoured as (1b) has high overvoltage. Thus splitting H_2S in alkaline solution is preferable to splitting water molecules. The efficiency in photocatalytic hydrogen generation can be improved by loading the semiconductor particles with platinum^{1,3,24,25,33-37}, sensitization of the semiconductors with dyes, e.g., $Ru(bipy)_3^{2+}$ ³⁸⁻⁴¹, mixing with a wide band gap semiconductor like TiO_2 ^{25,27,33}, ZnS ^{14-16,25,42-45} etc. Sacrificial substrates like sulphide^{1,16,25}, sulphite^{1,3,16,25}, EDTA²⁵, etc. have been used to prevent photocorrosion of the semiconductors.

Results and discussion

For photocatalytic generation of hydrogen, CdS was prepared from different sources and with different stoichiometric proportion. The results are presented in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively. From the results the CdS prepared from $Cd(CH_3COO)_2$ and Na_2S with 10% excess Cd^{2+} appears to be the most effective photocatalyst. Various materials were doped into the CdS prepared under this condition, to test the effect of these materials on the photocatalytic activity of CdS. The results are shown in Table 3. From the data in this table we can see that Ag_2S , Pt, Pd and RuO_2 have significant effect on the efficiency of hydrogen evolution. The joint effect of either ($Ag_2S + Pt$) or ($RuO_2 + Pt$) is more significant. The effect of variation of concentration of different dopants have been reported earlier^{37,43}. Though ZnS does not

Table 1. Evolution of hydrogen using CdS particles prepared with different cadmium salts and S^{2-}

Source of CdS	Volume of H_2 produced (ml g ⁻¹)
$CdCl_2, Na_2S$	3.95
$CdCl_2, H_2S$	3.55
$Cd(NO_3)_2, Na_2S$	4.00
$Cd(NO_3)_2, H_2S$	3.60
$CdSO_4, Na_2S$	4.05
$CdSO_4, H_2S$	3.50
$Cd(ClO_4)_2, Na_2S$	3.90
$Cd(ClO_4)_2, H_2S$	3.55
$Cd(CH_3COO)_2, Na_2S$	4.10
$Cd(CH_3COO)_2, H_2S$	3.66

Table 2. Effect of excess Cd^{2+} or S^{2-} in CdS on its photocatalytic activity

Source of CdS	Volume of H_2 produced (ml g ⁻¹)		
	Stoichiometric	Excess sulphide	Excess cadmium
$CdCl_2, Na_2S$	3.95	3.80	4.00
$Cd(NO_3)_2, Na_2S$	4.00	3.75	4.10
$CdSO_4, Na_2S$	4.00	3.80	4.05
$Cd(ClO_4)_2, Na_2S$	3.90	3.75	4.00
$Cd(CH_3COO)_2, Na_2S$	4.10	3.95	4.15

Table 3. Effect of different electron and hole transfer dopants in the semiconductor on the photocatalytic hydrogen generation

Dopant ^a	Volume of H_2 produced (ml g ⁻¹)
Nil	4.15
Ag_2S	4.50
HgS	4.15
CuS	4.00
Pt	4.95
Pd	4.55
RuO_2	4.45
$Ag_2S + Pt^b$	6.45
$RuO_2 + Pt^b$	6.00

^a1% of each dopant was loaded on CdS.

^b1% of platinum was doped on to CdS already loaded with Ag_2S or RuO_2 .

Table 4. Effect of composition variation of the semiconductor system CdS/ZnS on the photocatalytic hydrogen evolution

Wt ratio CdS : ZnS	Wt% of CdS	Wt% of ZnS	Volume of H_2 evolved (ml g ⁻¹)
1 : 0	100.0	0.0	4.15
6 : 1	85.7	14.3	8.55
5 : 1	83.3	16.7	11.50
4 : 1	80.0	20.0	12.15
3 : 1	75.0	25.0	14.10
2.5 : 1	71.4	28.6	16.75
2 : 1	66.7	33.3	16.45
1.5 : 1	60.0	40.0	23.65
1 : 1	50.0	50.0	21.05
1 : 1.5	40.0	60.0	17.00
1 : 2	33.3	66.7	13.95
1 : 2.5	28.6	71.4	14.75
1 : 3	25.0	75.0	18.30
1 : 4	20.0	80.0	21.65
1 : 5	16.7	83.3	16.50
1 : 6	14.3	85.7	15.75
0 : 1	0.0	100.0	0.0

absorb in the visible range of the solar spectrum, it exerts some very positive effect on CdS regarding photocatalytic hydrogen production^{14-16,25,42-45}. A detailed variation of composition of CdS and ZnS and their effect on hydrogen generation is presented in Table 4. CdS and ZnS in the weight ratio 1.5 : 1 has been found to be the most efficient among the compositions. The effect of Pt and Ag₂S on the mixed semiconductor CdS/ZnS were studied separately and the corresponding data are shown in Table 5. While for platinum, when 2% of it is doped in the mixed semiconductor produces the best result, for

variation in the semiconductor system were investigated and the results are given in Table 7.

Table 1 shows that samples obtained from different sources exhibit different photocatalytic activities; CdS, precipitated from Cd(CH₃COO)₂ and Na₂S being the most efficient photocatalyst in producing H₂. CdS particulates were also prepared by using 10% excess of either Cd^{II} salts or S²⁻ than the stoichiometric amounts. Results presented in Table 2 show that the use of excess Cd^{II} salts during the preparation of CdS powders yield photocatalysts slightly more efficient while the use of

Table 5. Effect of variation of Pt and Ag₂S concentration in mixed semiconductor CdS/ZnS^a on the photocatalytic hydrogen evolution

Percentage of Pt or Ag ₂ S loaded on CdS	Volume of H ₂ evolved (ml g ⁻¹)		Increase in efficiency compared to bare CdS mixed with ZnS	
	CdS doped with Pt	CdS doped with Ag ₂ S	CdS doped with Pt	CdS doped with Ag ₂ S
	0.0	23.65	23.65	-
0.5	29.50	26.80	24.74	13.32
1.0	35.15	28.75	48.63	21.56
1.5	40.00	30.10	69.13	27.27
2.0	40.20	29.95	69.98	26.64
2.5	37.70	27.45	59.41	16.07
3.0	34.05	26.80	43.97	13.32
3.5	31.75	22.55	34.25	-
4.0	31.45	21.80	32.98	-

^aCdS was first doped either with Pt or with Ag₂S and then this doped CdS was mechanically mixed with ZnS in the wt ratio 1.5 : 1.

Ag₂S it is 1.5%. The effect of hole scavengers viz. sodium formate and sodium oxalate were studied and compared the result with the effect produced by Ag₂S. The relevant data are presented in Table 6. Finally, the effect of incorporation of *n*-type silicon and its concentration

Table 6. Effect of hole scavengers on the generation of H₂ by mixed semiconductor photocatalyst Pt/CdS/ZnS^a
Time of illumination = 30 h

Scavenger	Volume of evolved (ml g ⁻¹)
Nil	24.0
Ag ₂ S ^b	31.0
0.02 M Sodium formate	32.0
0.02 M Sodium oxalate	32.5

^aThe catalyst was prepared by doping of 1.5% Pt on CdS and then mixing with ZnS in the ratio 1.5 : 1.

^bCdS was prepared along with 1.5% Ag₂S. The whole mixture was doped with 1.5% Pt.

Table 7. Effect of *n*-type Si concentration in CdS, CdS/Pt and CdS/Pt/ZnS on the photoelectrochemical production of hydrogen

Concentration of Si (wt%)	Volume of H ₂ produced (ml g ⁻¹)		
	CdS	CdS/Pt ^a	CdS/Pt/ZnS ^b
0	4.15	6.00	41.50
1	4.25	7.80	54.00
2	4.40	8.25	59.00
3	4.40	8.60	65.50
4	4.45	8.80	69.00
5	4.35	8.95	70.50
6	4.40	9.10	72.00
7	4.40	9.20	72.50
8	4.35	9.20	71.50
9	4.35	9.15	71.00
10	4.35	9.20	72.50

^aCdS was mixed with Si and then 1.5% platinum was doped.

^bCdS was mixed with Si and then 1.5% platinum was deposited followed by mixing with ZnS in the ratio 1.5 : 1.

excess Na_2S results in a slightly less efficiency. Serpone *et al.*²⁷ and Barbeni *et al.*³³ also noted that the source and nature of CdS dispersions have a remarkable effect on the rate of H_2 evolution. They observed CdS obtained from nitrate salt to be the most effective. In the present study, since CdS powders prepared from $\text{Cd}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ and Na_2S with 10% excess of Cd^{2+} was found to be the most effective photocatalyst (slightly more efficient than CdS prepared using $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$), in all subsequent experiments CdS particulates prepared following this method were used.

CdS alone, upon absorption of photons, produces electrons in the conduction band and holes in the valence band which are uniformly distributed through the CdS particles. Fendler *et al.*¹⁴ pointed out that these free delocalised carriers migrate to the particle surface and get trapped at the various surface sites or undergoes site-mediated recombinations among themselves. Subsequently, reduction of protons to H_2 takes place (eq. (1a)) by these trapped electrons in the surface states. The very low efficiency of naked CdS towards photocatalytic H_2 generation results from the presence of a large number of low-lying surface states (acceptor levels) that are ineffective towards hydrogen ion reduction. CdS is well-known to precipitate with a sulphur deficient stoichiometry, i.e. with S^{2-} vacancies. These positively charged sulphur vacancies may act as electron traps. The difference in photocatalytic activity of CdS powders obtained from different sources may be due to the difference in particle-size of different lots of CdS powders. Alternatively, the semiconductor photocatalysts may have different non-stoichiometric compositions, under different environmental conditions of preparations, which might affect the photocatalytic property. The various sources of CdS differ only in the counter ions in the cadmium salts (Table 1). The preparation techniques of the samples provoke inclusion of impurities. In the semiconductor samples the trap states may be created by the impurities where the sulphur ion is replaced by the counter ion of the cadmium salt. The replacement proceeds very easily if the size of the counter ion nearly equals the sulphur radius. Since the chlorine ions are of similar size to that of sulphur ions, the former may take the latter's place. In contrast, the inclusion of molecular groups more than thrice as large causes strong lattice deformations. In this situation the sulphur atom can hardly be substituted by the large acetate ions resulting in no such traps/surface states and the excited photoelectrons are now available in the conduc-

tion band edge and can efficiently reduce the hydrogen ions (eq. (1a)). On the other hand, small size chlorine ions replace similar size sulphur ions in the crystal lattice, forming low-lying surface states/traps and CdS cannot reduce the hydrogen ions efficiently. This can be justified with the observation that CdS obtained from chloride solution has lower luminescence intensity compared to CdS obtained from acetate solution. Hence, the choice of the counter ion of the cadmium salt represents a possibility to control the impurity luminescence. The use of large counter ions in the cadmium salts may consequently enhance the band-edge emission.

The hydrogen evolution efficiency of the photocatalysts is further enhanced by the deposition of platinum on the semiconductor particulates. The barrier height for electron transfer at the semiconductor/Pt interface is lower than that at the semiconductor/solution interface. This is advantageous for electron-hole separation. Moreover, the platinum surface has low overpotential for hydrogen evolution. These factors cause the higher efficiency in the evolution of hydrogen by semiconductor systems in contact with platinum.

Presence of a little amount of Ag_2S enhances the photocatalytic efficiency of CdS as is evident from Table 3 and Table 6. Reber *et al.*¹⁶ claim that the photocatalyst CdS coprecipitated with Ag_2S produce hydrogen more efficiently than CdS as such. This has been attributed to the fact that Ag_2S , owing to its having the same lattice structure as CdS, might facilitate the holes produced in the bulk of the semiconductor to move towards the semiconductor/electrolyte interface more easily as Ag_2S particles act as hole-transfer catalysts for the oxidation of sulphide. Our data presented in Table 7 corroborate this assumption. Results show that the presence of hole-scavengers like sodium formate or sodium oxalate liberates hydrogen with greater efficiency compared to that in presence of Ag_2S . The increase in the yield of hydrogen through use of hole-scavengers indirectly supports the theory of Reber *et al.*¹⁶ about the role of Ag_2S in facilitating hole transfer. The use of formate or oxalate is more economical as costly Ag_2S can be replaced by cheaper material such as sodium oxalate.

Holes, apart from reacting normally with the S^{2-}/S system, react with sodium formate or sodium oxalate since the reaction is thermodynamically favoured. So a greater number of holes are quenched due to the presence of sodium formate or sodium oxalate. Consequently a lesser

number of electron-hole recombinations result in the production of hydrogen at an increased rate. In the process of scavenging holes, formate/oxalate decomposes to CO₂ which gets absorbed in the alkaline medium.

ZnS itself cannot produce hydrogen photoelectrochemically by the absorption of solar radiations because of its high band gap. But its presence enhances the photocatalytic hydrogen production by CdS as seen from Table 5 and Table 6. Fendler *et al.*¹⁴ have suggested that ZnS, coated onto CdS, removes or repairs the surface states in CdS. Since the low-lying surface states are blocked by ZnS, there is an increased fraction of conduction band electrons available at a more negative potential for hydrogen production, resulting in improved hydrogen production efficiency. Alternatively, Bard *et al.*¹⁵ showed that during the formation of ZnS coated CdS, some Zn²⁺ ions get adsorbed on the CdS layer and proposed that Zn²⁺ in intimate contact with CdS is crucial for higher photocatalytic activity towards hydrogen generation. From a more negative value of the CdS flat band potential and an enhanced photocurrent in the presence of Zn²⁺, they have suggested that Zn²⁺ blocks CdS surface states, thereby resulting in an improvement in the photocatalytic activity of the semiconductor systems. Both the groups nevertheless agree, despite their difference in the mechanistic of the process about the non-availability of the low-lying surface states resulting in an increased availability of more energetic electrons for improved hydrogen production.

The enhanced photocatalytic production of hydrogen by CdS in the presence of *n*-type silicon is observed and may result from two processes. There is a fair chance of silicon being encased in a sheath of CdS or CdS/ZnS particles. The part of the solar radiation with wavelength longer than 520 nm (corresponding to the 2.4 eV band gap of CdS) passes through CdS or CdS/ZnS and excites electron from the valence band of silicon. Thus, a large fraction of the solar energy is utilised (since both CdS and Si absorbs different regions of the solar radiation) in producing hydrogen. Also, interparticle electron transferring between Si and CdS may make more electrons available for the reduction of protons. Gratzel *et al.*⁴⁶ proposed interparticle electron transfer to explain an enhancement in the rate of hydrogen production with CdS/TiO₂ mixed semiconductor system. Kamat and co-workers⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹ reported efficient electron-hole separation by coupling two semiconductor particles in colloidal form and explained their efficient electron-hole separation by interparticle electron transfer. Upon absorption of photons, electron-hole pairs are generated in CdS and subse-

quently recombinations of these electron-hole pairs take place. The energy emitted by the non-radiative recombinations of electron-hole pairs in CdS can promote electrons from the valence band to the conduction band of silicon. Fig. 1 presents the energy level diagram of CdS and Si. Since the conduction band levels of CdS and Si are almost isoenergetic (the conduction band of Si is slightly higher than that of CdS⁵⁰), transfer of hot electrons from the conduction band of Si may take place to

Fig. 1. Energy level diagram of CdS and Si.

that of CdS. Under such conditions, a greater number of electrons are available in the conduction band of CdS which can participate in proton reduction. The holes in the valence band of Si may be quenched by the electrons in the levels of *n*-CdS which lie below the Fermi level of CdS. Due to this quenching, the donor levels of CdS are stripped of electrons which are replenished by electrons being excited from the valence band of CdS upon visible light irradiation. The holes thus generated in the valence band of CdS react in turn with sulphide ions present in the solution. The sequence of reactions is presented in Scheme 1. The sequence of reactions, as proposed by us, causes the electron-hole separation in CdS to be more effective.

Scheme 1

Luminescence : Luminescence measurement provides important informations regarding semiconductor behaviours. Fig. 2 represents the luminescence spectra of bare CdS particles as well as CdS particles containing

Fig. 2. Luminescence spectra of semiconductor powders : (a) CdS, (b) Pd (1.5 wt%)/CdS, (c) Pt (1.5 wt%)/CdS and (d) CdS/Ag₂S (1.5 wt%). Excitation wavelength = 320 nm.

1.5% each of Pd, Pt and Ag₂S. The spectrum has an intense maximum at around 590 nm for CdS. However, a strong quenching of luminescence occurs without changing significantly the general nature of the spectrum when Pd, Pt or Ag₂S is introduced into CdS. The higher rate of electron-hole recombination results in higher luminescence intensity. The more efficient is the electron-hole separation in a semiconductor, the more is the photocatalytic activity. The lower luminescence intensity as a consequence, indicates higher photocatalytic activity of the semiconductors.

Luminescence in semiconductor particles is due to the recombination of electrons and holes. Provided it is assumed that the electron-hole recombination occurs by transition of electrons from the bottom of the conduction band to the top of the valence band, the luminescence spectra imply that the band gap energy of CdS is around 2.1 eV (emission at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 590$ nm corresponds to 2.1 eV). However, it is well known that the band gap of CdS is 2.4 eV. To test whether low band gap (2.1 eV) CdS has been formed under the experimental condition, reflectance spectral measurement was carried out for determining the band gap of the semiconductors. Analysis of the latter confirms the band gap of our CdS to be 2.404 eV

which agrees with the literature value. Thus from the reflectance spectral measurements it can be concluded that luminescence is not due to electron-hole recombination of an electron from the conduction band, rather it occurs from a level about 0.3 eV lower in energy than that in the conduction band. The combined studies of luminescence and reflectance spectral measurements thus support the assumption of the presence of surface states as described earlier in connection with the role of ZnS in enhancing the photocatalytic efficiency of CdS.

Experimental

Chemicals used, techniques for preparation of solutions and other experimental details are described elsewhere^{37,42,43}. Results reported in this paper are on the basis of irradiation of 100 mg of photocatalysts with exposed surface area 1.5 cm² and duration of irradiation 5 h unless mentioned otherwise.

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References

1. D. Hayes, F. Grieser and D. N. Furlong, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1990, **86**, 3637.
2. M. Matsumura, M. Hiramoto, T. Iehara and H. Tsubomura, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1984, **88**, 248.
3. T. Uchihara, M. Matsumura, A. Yamamoto and H. Tsubomura, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1989, **93**, 5870.
4. J. R. Harbour, R. Wolkow and M. L. Hair, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1981, **85**, 4026.
5. A. Sobczynski, A. J. Bard, A. Campion, M. A. Fox, T. Mallouk, S. E. Webber and J. M. White, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1987, **91**, 3316.
6. D. N. Furlong, F. Grieser, D. Hayes, R. Hayes, W. Sasse and D. Wells, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1986, **90**, 2388.
7. G. Bamwenda, A. M. Mika and T. Z. Winnicki, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1991, **36**, 153.
8. M. Matsumura, Y. Saho and H. Tsubomura, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1983, **87**, 3807.
9. E. Borgarello, N. Serpone, M. Barbeni, C. Minero, E. Pelizzetti and B. Pramauro, *La Chimica e L'Industria* **68**, October 1986.
10. N. Buhler, K. Meier and J. F. Reber, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1984, **88**, 3261.
11. J. F. Reber and K. Meier, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1984, **88**, 5903.
12. A. Sobczynski, A. Yildiz, A. J. Bard, A. Campion, M. A. Fox, T. Mallouk, S. E. Webber and J. M.

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- White, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1988, **92**, 2311.
13. A. Sobczynski, A. J. Bard, A. Campion, M. A. Fox, T. Mallouk, S. E. Webber and J. M. White, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1989, **93**, 401.
 14. H.-C. Youn, S. Baral and J. H. Fendler, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1988, **92**, 6320.
 15. (a) N. Kakuta, K.-H. Park, M. F. Finlayson, A. Ueno, A. J. Bard, A. Campion, M. A. Fox, S. E. Webber and J. M. White, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1985, **89**, 732; (b) N. Kakuta, K.-H. Park, M. F. Findlayson, A. J. Bard, A. Campion, M. A. Fox, S. E. Webber and J. M. White, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1985, **89**, 5028.
 16. J. F. Reber and M. Rusek, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1984, **90**, 824.
 17. L. Borrell, S. C. March, J. Gimenez, R. Simarro and J. M. Andujar, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*, 1992, **25**, 25.
 18. (a) B. Kraeutler and A. J. Bard, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 303; 1978, **100**, 2239.
 19. T. Kawai and T. Sakata, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1979, 1047.
 20. I. Izumi, F. F. Fan and A. J. Bard, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1981, **85**, 218.
 21. T. Sakata and T. Kawai, *J. Synth. Org. Chem.*, 1981, **85**, 218.
 22. S. Sato and J. M. White, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1980, **83**, 72.
 23. S. Sato and J. M. White, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1981, **85**, 336.
 24. T. Sakata, T. Kawai and K. Hassimoto, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1982, **88**, 50.
 25. J. Sabate, S. Cervera-March, R. Simarro and J. Gimenez, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, 1990, **15**, 115.
 26. E. N. Savinov, Y. A. Gruzdkov and V. N. Parmon, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, 1989, **14**, 1.
 27. N. Serpone, E. Borgarello, M. Barbeni and E. Pelizzetti, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1984, **90**, 191.
 28. K. Kalyanasundaram, E. Borgarello and M. Gratzel, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1981, **64**, 362.
 29. J. R. Darwent and G. Porter, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1981, 145.
 30. W. Hetterich and H. Kisch, *Photochem. Photobiol.* 1990, **52**, 631.
 31. A. Hanglein and Gutierrez, *Ber. Bunsenges. Phys. Chem.*, 1983, **87**, 852.
 32. B. Kraeutler and A. J. Bard, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1977, **81**, 1484.
 33. M. Barbeni, E. Pelizzetti, E. Borgarello, N. Serpone, M. Gratzel, L. Balducci and M. Visca, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, 1985, **10**, 249.
 34. E. Borgarello, K. Kalyanasundaram, M. Gratzel and E. Pelizzetti, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1982, **65**, 243.
 35. A. W.-H. Mau, C.-B. Huang, N. Kakuta, A. J. Bard, A. Campion, M. A. Fox, J. M. White and S. E. Webber, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **106**, 6537.
 36. K. Krishan, J. R. White, M. A. Fox and A. J. Bard, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **105**, 7002.
 37. G. C. De and A. M. Roy, *J. Surface Sci. Technol.*, 1999, **15**, 146.
 38. J. Desilvestro, M. Gratzel, M. Kavan and J. Moser, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **107**, 2988.
 39. L. Loy and E. E. Wolf, *Solar Energy*, 1985, **34**, 455.
 40. C. Minero, E. Lorenzi, E. Pramauro and E. Pelizzetti, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1984, **91**, 301.
 41. R. M. Quint and N. Getoff, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, 1988, **13**, 269.
 42. A. M. Roy and G. C. De, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 2003, **15**, 146.
 43. (a) G. C. De, A. M. Roy and S. S. Bhattacharya, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, 1995, **20**, 127; 1996, **21**, 19.
 44. A. Ueno, N. Kakuta, K.-H. Park, M. F. Finlayson, A. J. Bard, A. Campion, M. A. Fox, S. E. Webber and J. M. White, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1985, **89**, 3828.
 45. M. F. Finlayson, B. L. Wheeler, N. Kakuta, K.-H. Park, A. J. Bard, A. Campion, M. A. Fox, S. E. Webber and J. M. White, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1985, **89**, 5676.
 46. N. Serpone, E. Borgarello and M. Gratzel, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1984, 342.
 47. P. V. Kamat and B. Patrick, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1992, **96**, 6829.
 48. S. Hotchandani and P. V. Kamat, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1992, **96**, 6834.
 49. K. R. Gopidas, M. Bohorquez and P. V. Kamat, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1990, **94**, 6435.
 50. J.-M. Lehn, in J. S. Connolly (ed.), "Photochemical Conversion and Storage of Solar Energy", Academic Press, New York, 1981, Chap. 6.

